

Building an ontology for cardiovascular diseases

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Abstract-The semantic web is an extension of the World Wide Web. The purpose of the semantic web is to make data on the web understandable for computers. Ontology is the main tool used in the semantic web. Ontology refers to the state of being. In the field of medicine, ontology describes the concepts of terminologies used in medicine. Many papers present ontologies that describe the relationships between medical concepts, which thus enables the sharing of medical information. The use of ontologies in the field of medicine and healthcare is evolving. This paper will introduce the development process of an ontology for the cardiovascular diseases.

Index Terms-cardiovascular diseases, medicine, ontology, semantic web

I. INTRODUCTION

The variety and diversity of information brings various problems and one of the most important ones is the speed and accuracy in finding information. The semantic network provides a format or structure that can help computers understand data, so to get the meaning of what is in the document and not just transmit the information as it currently happens on the existing web. One of the main and essential technologies of the semantic network is "ontology". An ontology defines a common vocabulary for all researchers who share and need to share information in a given field. This dictionary includes interpreted definitions of basic concepts of the field as well as the relationships between them.

Ontologies can be applied in various fields such as computer science or other fields of interest. Recently the application of ontologies in the field of medicine has been noticed. The application of ontologies in the field of medicine is constantly evolving, doing various researches and developments. This paper focuses on the semantic network as well as ontologies, mainly on the various developments of ontologies in the field of medicine and the research that has been done on them. This paper presents the design, development and construction of an ontology for cardiovascular diseases.

II. SEMANTIC WEB AND ONTOLOGIES

From the moment the semantic network was conceived and created, the close connection between it and the traditional web is clearly seen. As one of Tim Berners-Lee quotes says, the semantic web is simply an extension of that huge space called the World Wide Web [1]. On the traditional web if we search for an information, page or document, we will get different answers which may match our search based on the specific words required, but this process is not always effective as the results we get not always match what we ask for, also the amount of data we get is bigger than what we can actually manage. As it is known, the language currently used on the web is the markup language - HTML, which uses a description of documents, which in computer language is just text without real meaning.

A. Semantic Web

The semantic web provides a format or structure that can help computers understand data, that is, to get the meaning of what is in the document and not just to transmit the information. This semantic web adds metadata and

new data to existing documents on the web, turning these documents into comprehensible data for computers. Real-world people, places, and objects in the semantic web can be referenced by a variety of identifiers. Through the different technologies it offers, the semantic web allows and performs the expansion of information or concepts in different time periods, performed by different communities and using different vocabulary.

Figure 1. Traditional Web Vs Semantic Web.

B. Ontologies

A main reason for growing interest in ontologies is the development of the semantic web [1]. One of the main and essential technologies of the semantic web is "ontology". Ontology comes from the Greek word "onto" which means "to be" and "logia" which means "word" [2]. In computer science one of the most popular definitions and why it was thought and discussed as an incomplete definition is that of Thomas Gruber, who defines ontology "as a formal and clear specification of a conceptualization in a certain field of interest" [3]. This definition emphasizes two key points: [4]

1. Conceptualization is formal and thus allows reasoning by the computer.
2. A practical ontology is designed for specific areas of interest.

Since Gruber's definition was called incomplete, other authors have improved this definition-interpretation, making it more complete and expressive. Among them we mention Borst, who defined ontology as a "formal specification of a common conceptualization" [5]. According to the many interpretations made, by ontology we mean a set of concepts which are hierarchically related together based on the relationships of these concepts within the area of interest [6]. Some of the reasons why an ontology should be developed are [7]:

1. Sharing information and knowledge for the same field.
2. Enabling the reuse of field knowledge.
3. Clarification of field expressions.
4. Separation of field knowledge from operational knowledge.
5. Analysis of field knowledge.

There is no exact way or specific methodology for developing ontologies, however there are some basic rules in designing them. Although these rules seem incontestable, they help in making decisions on the design process of ontologies [7] :

1. No exact way of modeling- There is no exact way of modeling an ontology. There are always different alternatives, depending on the application to be built.
2. Iterative process- The development of ontologies should be an iterative process.
3. Concepts- In ontology concepts should be close to objects which may be physical or logical and relationships in the field of interest.

C. *Ontological languages*

When we talk about semantics and semantic knowledge, seems the need for a language that can represent, codify and manage semantic knowledge. Numerous attempts have been made to create multiple languages that could represent, codify, and manage semantic knowledge, but most languages have been based on logic [8]. An important language used before was Ontolingua, which has been the most popular language for presenting or reflecting ontologies enabling the presentation of concepts, taxonomies of concepts, relations, functions, axioms, instances and procedures. Ontolingua was considered a de facto standard by the ontology community in 1990. Another well-known language is the LOOM language, developed at the same time as Ontolingua, which is a language for the general presentation of knowledge based mainly on descriptive logic as well as in the rules of production and automatic classification of concepts. The World Wide Web development led to the creation of ontological languages for utilizing web features. Such languages are commonly referred to as web-based ontological languages or ontological markup languages. Their syntax is based on markup languages such as HTML and XML, the purpose of which is not ontological development, but the presentation and exchange of data.

RDF stands as a standard model introduced by the W3C for web data sharing. RDF is intended to represent metadata about web resources, such as title, author, date of modification of a web page, copyright and licensing of a web document, or availability time for some of the common sources. However, by generalizing the concept of a web resource, RDF can also be used to present information about things that can be identified on the web, even when they cannot be archived directly on it. The basic concepts of RDF are: Resources, Attributes / Properties, Formulations [9].

RDFS is a semantic extension of RDF, providing a model-data dictionary for RDF data, so defining an ontological dictionary in the form of classes, class properties, and the relationships between them. RDFS provides mechanisms to describe interconnected resource groups as well as the relationships between such resources. These resources are used to determine the characteristics of other resources, such as the domain and the range of characteristics.

OWL is built by the W3C. It is a markup language for publishing and sharing ontologies on the web. OWL was developed as an extension of the RDF dictionary and it comes from DAML + OIL OWL [10]. The OWL language facilitates machine interpretation of web content compared to RDF and RDFS, providing additional vocabulary with formal semantics: relationships between classes, different types of properties (ObjectProperty and DatatypeProperty), class counting, etc. In OWL there are two types of properties [11]: object properties that connect

the instances and objects of a class with other objects, datatype properties that associate objects with data type values.

III. ONTOLOGIES IN HEALTHCARE

Numerous advances and changes in computer technology as well as in healthcare in recent years have expanded and improved the data of the traditional field of medical services. Ontology is the study of categories of things that exist or may exist in several areas. It is a catalog of the kinds of things that can exist in a field of interest D seen from the perspective of a person who uses X language to speak precisely about the field of interest D. The types in ontology represent predicates, senses of words or concepts and X language connection types when used to discuss topics in field D [12].

The importance of ontology is known in various fields, these areas are directed towards practice, such as knowledge engineering, knowledge representation, qualitative modeling, language engineering, database design, information integration, object oriented analysis, recovery of information and knowledge, etc. Currently the areas in which the application of ontologies is observed are: natural language translation, mechanical engineering, e-commerce, geographic information systems, legal information systems and last but not least in the field of biology and medicine [13]. Application of ontologies in the field of medicine has recently been noticed. The use of ontologies in medicine focuses mainly on the representation and (re) organization of medical terminology [14]. Doctors and specialists have developed specific languages and vocabularies to help them, to efficiently store and communicate general knowledge in the field of medicine and healthcare as well as information related to patients. These specific languages and vocabulary are easily understood by people, mainly specialists in the field, and are characterized by a considerable amount of implicit knowledge. On the other hand, the information systems used in the field of medicine must be able to communicate specific, complex and detailed medical concepts, which can often be expressed in different languages. Creating and building an ontology for the representation of medical terminology systems will enable in-depth analysis of the structure and concepts of medical terminology and will provide a solution by facilitating the communication of concepts. Some positive aspects of using ontology in the field of medicine are listed below:

1. Ontology can help to build more powerful and interactive information systems in healthcare.
2. Ontology can support the need for the healthcare process to transmit, reuse, and share patient data.
3. Ontology can provide semantics-based criteria to support different statistical aggregations for different purposes.
4. Ontologies can bring significant benefits supporting the necessary integration of knowledge and data.

Ontology in the field of medicine has its positive sides, as noted and described above, however there are those who are skeptical about the impact that ontologies can have on the design and maintenance of healthcare information systems in the world.

A. *Cardiovascular Diseases Ontology*

Before starting to build the ontology on cardiovascular disease some rules need to be analyzed and followed. As noted, there is no exact way or methodology in building and developing an ontology. There are always different alternatives which vary based on the application or field in which the ontology will be built. The development of

ontology itself should be a repetitive process, and it should also keep in mind that concepts in ontology should be close to objects which may be physical or logical and relationships in the field of interest. Building the ontology begins by specifying a work order. Firstly, some essential questions are raised, some of which are listed below:

1. What is the field that the ontology will cover?
2. What will the ontology be used for? What is its purpose?
3. What questions will the information contained in the ontology answer?
4. Who will use and maintain the built ontology?

The answers to these questions may not be unchangeable, they may change during the design and development of the ontology, but they are always needed and should get an answer whenever we think of changing something along the way of building the ontology by helping to limit the model field. One way to determine the scope of ontology is to outline a list of questions that some ontology-based knowledge should be able to answer competency questions. So it is not necessary to expand with a lot of information. Their purpose is to help us understand the scope, content and serve as a form of preliminary evaluation. The answer to these questions makes us better understand how accurate and useful the created ontology is. The concrete ontology to be built covers the field of medicine and is specifically the ontology of cardiovascular diseases. The design and construction of the ontology will be shown step by step, accompanied by pictures and comments which show the actions taken.

The answers to the above questions are:

1. What is the field that the ontology will cover? The field that the ontology will cover is the field of medicine, mainly diseases of the internal cardiovascular system.
2. What will the ontology be used for? What is its purpose? The ontology will be used to provide a basic model for the field of diseases of the cardiovascular system. This model will be used in diagnosing heart disease or diseases of the cardiovascular system.
3. What questions will the information contained in the ontology answer? This ontology will answer some questions like:
 - What are some of the cardiovascular diseases?
 - What are the symptoms of a disease?
 - What is the recommended treatment for a particular patient?
 - Who are the patients with a certain disease?
 - What is the right treatment for a particular disease?
 - What are the symptoms of the disease displayed in a patient?
4. Who will use and maintain the built ontology? The ontology can be used by doctors, medical students who can help diagnosing diseases for a particular patient. As well as can serve as a reference for researchers in the field.

The ontology is built through Protégé. The classes in ontology are two. There are six subclasses, of which two belong to the first class which is the Patient class, and four belong to the second class which is the Cardiovascular_Diseases class.

Figure 2. Ontology classes

A patient can be anyone who has a health problem and can be female or male. The Cardiovascular_Diseases class is the class which holds all the data on cardiovascular diseases, like the various cardiovascular diseases that may exist (Types_of_Diseases), medication that a particular disease has (treatment), various causes affecting the appearance of cardiovascular disease (Etiology), certain symptoms of a cardiovascular disease (Clinical_Causes). Object properties serve to connect two instances. Both domain and range will be classes. “Fig 3.” shows these object properties.

Figure 3. Object properties

Object properties constructed for the ontology of cardiovascular diseases are as follows:

- caused_by - domain: Types_of_Diseases, range: Etiology
- recommended_medication - domain: Patient, range: Treatment
- has_treatment - domain: Types_of_Diseases, range: Treatment
- has_symptoms - domain: Patient, range: Clinical_Causes
- has_disease - domain: Patient, range: Types_of_Diseases
- has_diagnosis: domain: Types_of_Diseases, range: Clinical_Causes

Data Properties describe the connection between instances and values data. Some of the data properties are shown in “Fig 4”.

Figure 4. Data properties

The domain will be a class and the range will be a value such as an integer or a string.

- hereditary - domain: Types_of_Diseases, range: boolean
- active_life - domain: Patient, range: boolean
- smoker - domain: Patient, range: boolean
- blood_pressure - domain: Patient, range: string
- weight - domain: Patient, range: integer
- age – domain: Patient, range: integer
- name – domain: Patient, range: string

The addition of individuals is done by defining their type, the class or subclass to which they belong. The population of ontology with data is made through Data Property Assertions. “Fig. 5” shows some individuals of ontology.

Figure 5. Individuals

“Fig. 6” shows the ontograph of the cardiovascular diseases ontology. Ontograph presents all existing links such as: class-subclass, object property or data property. “Fig. 7” shows the ontology metrics as a summary for the cardiovascular diseases ontology and shows all the key information on the created ontology.

Figure 6. Ontograph

Ontology metrics:	
Metrics	
Axiom	121
Logical axiom count	75
Declaration axioms count	46
Class count	8
Object property count	6
Data property count	7
Individual count	25
Annotation Property count	0
DL expressivity	ALC(D)
Class axioms	
SubClassOf	6
EquivalentClasses	0
DisjointClasses	1
GCI count	0
Hidden GCI Count	0
Object property axioms	
SubObjectPropertyOf	0

Figure 7. Ontology metrics

IV. CONCLUSIONS

One of the areas of interest which has changed being improved day by day is the field of medicine. These changes in this field are closely related to information technology, as information on this field are numerous and easily accessible to most people and the tools, programs and equipment used in this field are very more sophisticated thanks to IT changes. If we go back to the technologies offered by the semantic network, one of them is the ontology, which is nothing but a common vocabulary for all researchers who share and need to share information in a certain field. In this article is analyzed the connection between ontology and the field of healthcare. Emphasis was placed on the fact that the creation and construction of an ontology in the field of medicine for the representation of medical terminology systems will enable in-depth analysis of the structure and concepts of medical terminology, and will provide a solution in facilitating the communication of concepts and problems came across.

In this paper was presented the construction of a basic ontology on cardiovascular diseases. This ontology can serve as an information base for anyone who is interested in knowing more about the field of semantic network and ontologies and mainly for researchers who want to further expand research and work on the development of ontologies in the field of medicine.

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